

SHORT NOTES

Potentiometric Study on the Stability of Cr(III) Complexes of Glycine, Leucine, Valine, and Lysine

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Cr(III)-amino-acid complexes have not been extensively investigated. The only reaction deserving attention is the one between chromic chloride and alanine¹⁻⁶. Results of our previous studies⁷ on complexes other than alanine reveal the existence of 1:3 and 1:1 complexes of lysine, leucine, and aspartic acid. The present work is an extension of those studies and deals with the stability of the complexes obtained on refluxing normal chromic chloride with glycine, leucine, valine, and lysine for 24 hours at 80°.

Procedure.—CrCl₃ and KOH, both of A. R. reagent, and amino-acids (B.D.H.) were used to prepare the solutions. Absorption experiments and pH measurements were carried out respectively with Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 and Beckman pH-meter (model H2).

Employing Job's method⁸ of continued variations (wave lengths selected, 550 mμ by Vosburgh and Cooper's method⁹), the combining ratio for this reaction was found to be 1:3 (Cr³⁺:HSc⁻); solutions used were of 1.0M, 0.1M, and 0.01M. This very molar ratio was used for the three other amino-acids in applying Bjerrum's method.

For the stability determination, glycine (11.26 g.) was refluxed with M-CrCl₃ (100 ml) and water (300 ml) for 24 hr. at 80°. A portion (15 ml) of this solution was taken in pyrex boiling tubes and aliquots of 1.22M-KOH were added. The tubes were corked and heated for 24 hr. in an oil bath. The pHs of the products, so obtained, were immediately measured. Experiments with other amino-acids were carried out similarly, differing only in the amounts taken (8.447 g. leucine and 200 ml of 0.11M CrCl₃; 5.8575 g. valine and 0.0833M-CrCl₃; 7.306 g. lysine and 200 ml of 0.066M-CrCl₃).

The nature of the products formed are shown below:

(i) *Glycine*: In the pH range 3.2-5.3, the complex was soluble and violet in colour; from pH 6.65 to 9.15, a violet precipitate was obtained and beyond this range, Cr(OH)₃ was precipitated.

(ii) *Leucine*: A soluble, violet complex only was obtained in the narrow pH range of 4.55-4.85; from pH 4.85 to 9.2, a violet precipitate was obtained.

1. Tohongaefi and Serbin, *Compt. rend.*, 1910, 151, 1361.
2. Hugouneq and Morel, *ibid.*, 1912, 154, 110.
3. Ley and Ficken, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 377.
4. Shuttleworth, *J. Intern. Soc. Leather Trades Chem.*, 1948, 32, 116.
5. Serfass et al., *J. Amer. Leather Chem. Assoc.*, 1949, 44, 647.
6. Green and Ang, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 5482.
7. Malik and Khan, *Curr. Sci.*, 1960, 29, 135.
8. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.
9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 43.

(iii) *Valine*: A soluble, violet complex in the pH range of 4.80-5.75 was obtained; beyond this range either a green solution (pH 7.75) or a green precipitate (pH 8.55 to 10.0) was obtained.

(iv) *Lysine*: A soluble, light violet complex was obtained in the pH range of 3.8 to 6.5; beyond it a dark green solution (pH 8.1 to 8.9) or a green precipitate (pH 9.25 to 10.3) was obtained.

For determining the stability constant of the complexes, a plot was made between $\bar{n}$ and $-\log S_c$ (the values of $\bar{n}$ and $\log S_c$ were calculated by Albert's method¹⁰). The values of pK_1 , pK_2 , pK_{s_1} , and pK_{s_2} were found by extrapolating the value of $\log S_c$ at $\bar{n}=1.5$, 0.5, 2.0, and 1.0 respectively. The results are summarised below:

(i) *Glycine*: The value of $\bar{n}$ and $-\log S_c$ is linear, but from the point where precipitation occurs, a deviation in the curve is observed.

(ii) *Leucine*: The shape of the curve differs considerably; up to $\bar{n}=0.3$, no precipitation occurs; after that a violet precipitate is formed (probably the complex is precipitated). The value of $\bar{n}$, however, can be taken to be unity if the whole pH range is considered.

(iii) *Valine*: Precipitation occurs after the maximum value for $\bar{n}$ being 1.6.

(iv) *Lysine*: Precipitation starts after $\bar{n}=1.4$ and the value of $\bar{n}$ tends to a maximum of 1.73.

The values of the stability constants, as determined, are recorded in Table I.

Amino-acid.	pK_1 .	pK_2 .	pK_{s_1} .	pK_{s_2} .
Glycine	6.05	7.25	5.55	6.65
Leucine	..	5.30	..	1.30
Valine	3.10	4.95	..	3.60
Lysine	1.95	4.40	..	2.12

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